

A Prospective Randomized Comparative Study on Video Laryngoscopy and Direct Laryngoscopy during Endotracheal Intubation

Karthik G.¹, B. Ravindran², Murali Magesh Venugopal³, Nafeesa Maqbool⁴

¹DNB Anaesthesiology, Registrar, MGM Healthcare, Chennai

²Associate Professor, Department of Anesthesiology, Panimalar medical College hospital and research institute, Chennai

³Consultant Anaesthesiologist, Kauvery Hospital, Alwarpet, Chennai

⁴Assistant Professor, Panimalar Medical College Hospital and Research Institute, Chennai

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Nafeesa Maqbool

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Endotracheal intubation is one of the most common procedures done to secure the airway in patients requiring general anesthesia for surgery for which the traditional method of direct laryngoscope or modern video laryngoscopes are used. In this comparative study, we check the efficacy of video laryngoscope in improving the success rate of intubation over direct laryngoscope.

Objectives: Primarily we aim to compare the glottic visualization and time for intubation using both video laryngoscope and direct laryngoscope. As a secondary outcome, we observe the degree of alterations in hemodynamic responses to intubation using both video laryngoscopes and direct laryngoscopes.

Materials and Methods: A randomized prospective observational study conducted at a private hospital, Chennai within period of 2 months. The study population was 102 patients of either sex aged 20-85 years of which 51 were recruited for intubation using video laryngoscope(Group A) and remaining 51 with direct laryngoscope(Group B). Statistical analysis was done using independent samples t-test and Chi-square test.

Results: Mean time for glottic view was 25.00 seconds in group A compared to 36.75 seconds in group B. Mean time for intubation in group A was 50.14 seconds and in group B it was 69.92 seconds. We observed full laryngeal view significantly more in group A (84.3%) than in group B (64.7%). Ease of intubation was found to be easier in group A (68.6%) than in group B (54.9%). Regarding hemodynamic responses, there was statistically significant difference between two groups after intubation for the mean heart rate and for mean systolic blood pressure.

Conclusion: In this study, we observed significant reduction in time for intubation and improved glottic visualization using video laryngoscope, thus improving success rate of intubation compared to direct laryngoscope.

Keywords: Video Laryngoscope, Intubation, Glottic Visualization, Direct Laryngoscope, Airway.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Endotracheal intubation is one of the most common methods used to secure the airway in patients undergoing general anesthesia for surgery, and it is regarded as the gold standard for patients requiring long-term breathing assistance.

Direct laryngoscopy is the gold standard, since it allows for viewing of the vocal cords after elevating the epiglottis with a curved blade. However, improved laryngoscopy techniques have evolved throughout time and shown to be more successful [1].

Video laryngoscopy is an advanced method that employs a camera mounted to the blade's tip to broadcast an exterior image of the airway onto a screen. Video laryngoscopy allows for a clearer

anterior view of the glottis and a larger field of vision of the larynx [2]. Intubation using direct laryngoscopy necessitates alignment of the oral, pharyngeal, and laryngeal axes, which may be a challenge for the anesthetist in challenging airway settings, while a video laryngoscope can be employed because alignment is not required [3].

Video laryngoscopy gives a higher-resolution glottic picture than direct laryngoscopy [4]. Assistants may now examine the picture and simply coordinate with the operator [5].

It can serve as an effective teaching tool for residents undergoing postgraduate training under the guidance of an experienced anesthetist [6]. The current study was undertaken to compare the video

laryngoscopy and direct laryngoscopy during endotracheal intubation among people undergoing elective surgical procedure under general anaesthesia.

Materials and Methods

It is a randomized prospective observational study conducted at Kauvery Hospital, Chennai for two months from 16th April 2023 to 15th June 2023. Written informed consent was obtained from all the patients before the surgery and ethical approval was obtained. One hundred and two patients of ASA physical status 1,2 and 3 undergoing elective surgical procedure under general anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation were included in this study and divided into 2 groups.

Group A consists of 51 patients for whom video laryngoscope was used for intubation and Group B consists of 51 patients for whom direct laryngoscopy was done for intubation.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Age 20 to 85 years
2. ASA physical status 1,2 and 3 posted for elective surgical procedure under general anaesthesia

Exclusion Criteria

1. Unwilling patients
2. Patients on beta blockers
3. Anticipated difficult airway (Limited mouth opening <4cm, Mallampati grade 4, Restricted neck extension).

Statistical analysis was done using SPSS software. To compare mean values between groups, independent samples t-test is applied. To compare proportions between study and control groups, Chi-Square test is applied. If any expected cell frequency is less than five then Fisher's exact test is used. P-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Both the groups (A and B) consists of 51 patients each. They comprised both sexes similar in distribution (p=0.692) in the age group of 20 to 85

years. As per the table 1 & Fig 1, Group A patients comprised of mallampati grade 2 with (70.6%) (n=36); Group B patients of grade 2 with (74.5%) (n=38) and Group A of MP grade 3 with (29.4%)(n=15); Group B of grade 3 with (25.5%)(n=13).

Group A (84.3%) (n=43) showed full laryngeal view grade and Group B comprised of (64.7%) patients (n=33). Group A had shown significantly better glottic visualization during intubation than group B (p=0.023).

As per the table 2 & fig. 2, Intubation was found to be easier in group A (68.6%) (n=35) than group B (54.9%) (n=28). There was no statistically significant difference in ease of intubation between the two groups as p=0.279. The requirement of bougie for intubation was found to be more in group A (11.8%) (n=6) as compared to group B (9.8%) (n=5). The number of intubation attempts was lesser in group A (9.8%) than group B (11.8%). There was no significant difference in requirement of bougie and number of intubation attempts between the two groups.

As per the table 3, fig. 3 & fig. 4. The mean time for glottic visualization during intubation was significantly lesser in group A (25.00 sec) than group B (36.75 sec) as p-value was.

Mean time to intubation was significantly lesser in group A (50.14 sec) as compared to group B (69.92 sec) (p<0.001). As per the table 4 & fig. 5, the mean heart rate between the two groups had significant difference at all intervals from two to five minutes after intubation except at preinduction and at 1 min.

As per the table 5 & fig. 6, Mean systolic blood pressure had a significant difference between the two groups at 1 min after intubation.

As per the table 6 & fig. 7, Mean diastolic pressure had no significant difference between the two groups at all intervals from induction till 5 mins. All the patients were recovered well from anesthesia and none of them developed complications.

Table 1: Mallampatti grade and Laryngeal view grade

		Group						p-value
		Group A		Group B		Total		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	
Mallampati grade	Grade 2	36	70.6%	38	74.5%	74	72.5%	0.657
	Grade 3	15	29.4%	13	25.5%	28	27.5%	
	Total	51	100.0%	51	100.0%	102	100.0%	
Laryngeal view grade	Full	43	84.3%	33	64.7%	76	74.5%	0.023
	Partial	8	15.7%	18	35.3%	26	25.5%	
	Total	51	100.0%	51	100.0%	102	100.0%	

Figure 1: Mallampati grade and Laryngeal view grade

Table 2: Ease of intubation

		Group						p-value
		Group A		Group B		Total		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	
Ease of intubation	Easy	35	68.6%	28	54.9%	63	61.8%	0.279
	Modified (Burp)	5	9.8%	12	23.5%	17	16.7%	
	Modified (>1 attempt)	5	9.8%	6	11.8%	11	10.8%	
	Total	51	100.0%	51	100.0%	102	100.0%	
Ease of intubation	Easy	35	68.6%	28	54.9%	63	61.8%	0.154
	Modified	16	31.4%	23	45.1%	39	38.2%	
	Total	51	100.0%	51	100.0%	102	100.0%	

Figure 2: Ease of Intubation

Table 3: Time to glottis view and Time to intubation

	Group	N	Mean	Std Dev	p-value
Time to glottis view (sec)	Group A	51	25.00	8.653	<0.001
	Group B	51	36.75	11.101	
Time to intubation	Group A	51	50.14	13.430	<0.001
	Group B	51	69.92	18.330	

Figure 3: Mean time to glottis view

Figure 4: Mean time to intubation

Table 4: Difference in heart rate between group A and group B

	Group	N	Mean	Std Dev	p-value
Heart rate (beats/min) at pre induction	Group A	51	72.06	11.846	0.369
	Group B	51	74.25	12.729	
Heart rate (beats/min) at 1 min	Group A	51	78.84	13.690	0.064
	Group B	51	83.75	12.696	
Heart rate (beats/min) at 2 mins	Group A	51	77.94	11.080	0.046
	Group B	51	82.41	11.296	
Heart rate (beats/min) at 3 mins	Group A	51	72.10	9.851	0.007
	Group B	51	77.51	10.051	
Heart rate (beats/min) at 4 mins	Group A	51	68.82	10.365	0.022
	Group B	51	73.84	11.451	
Heart rate (beats/min) at 5 mins	Group A	51	66.78	10.310	0.034
	Group B	51	71.53	11.947	

Figure 5: Mean heart rate (beats/min)

Table 5: Difference in mean systolic blood pressure

	Group	N	Mean	Std Dev	p-value
S BP (mmhg) at pre induction	Group A	49	136.92	19.423	
	Group B	51	143.04	20.465	0.129
S BP (mmhg) at 1 n	Group A	51	135.76	19.878	0.029
	Group B	51	144.33	19.291	
BP (mmhg) at 2 ns	Group A	51	133.98	18.354	0.194
	Group B	51	138.86	19.357	
BP (mmhg) at 3 s	Group A	51	128.84	14.016	0.301
	Group B	50	132.24	18.550	
BP (mmhg) at 4 is	Group A	51	122.41	16.116	0.422
	Group B	51	125.10	17.478	
BP (mmhg) at 5 S	Group A	50	120.54	14.694	0.453
	Group B	51	122.92	16.946	

Table 6: Difference in mean diastolic blood pressure

	Group	N	Mean	Std Dev	p-value
Dias BP (mmhg) at pre induction	Group A	51	78.88	13.557	
	Group B	51	82.80	12.058	0.126
Dias BP (mmhg) at 1 min	Group A	51	78.59	12.922	
	Group B	51	77.29	21.652	0.715
Dias BP (mmhg) at 2 mins	Group A	51	77.29	11.432	
	Group B	51	79.88	11.387	0.255
Dias BP (mmhg) at 3 mins	Group A	51	73.73	8.962	
	Group B	51	74.35	11.162	0.755
Dias BP (mmhg) at 4 mins	Group A	51	68.73	11.785	
	Group B	51	71.67	9.887	0.175
Dias BP (mmhg) at 5 mins	Group A	51	66.76	12.278	
	Group B	51	68.71	9.954	0.383

Figure 6: Mean systolic pressure difference

Figure 7: Mean diastolic pressure difference

Discussion

Video laryngoscopy offers an excellent image of the larynx during intubation. In recent decades, video laryngoscopy techniques have been applied in various endoscopic ways to provide a better anatomical image, delineate defects, and facilitate team collaboration. This benefit is lacking in conventional laryngoscopy, making the assistant's participation problematic. When compared to direct laryngoscopy, video laryngoscopy has a greater success rate on the first try and takes less time to intubate.

Maria Vargas and team [7] examined 97 randomized controlled studies including 12775 patients and found that videolaryngoscopy dramatically reduced the risk of difficult intubation while increasing the probability of first-time

intubation success when compared to direct Macintosh laryngoscopy. Maria Michailidou and team [8] conducted a comparison of video and direct laryngoscopy for emergency intubation in trauma patients. The study comprised 709 trauma patients who were intubated using either VL or DL. The total success rate of intubation with VL was 88% compared to DL (83%) (P = 0.05). Cervical spine immobilization predicted better initial success with VL (87%) than with DL (80%) (P < 0.05). Depending on the specific laryngoscope, a video laryngoscope may cause less neck movement than a direct laryngoscope. Roya Yumul and team [9] conducted a prospective randomized controlled trial using three VL devices (Video-Mac VL, Glide Scope A VL, and McGrath VL) to compare direct laryngoscopy for intubating 121 obese patients with a BMI more than 30 kg/m² having bariatric

surgery. All three VL devices improved glottic views compared to standard DL ($p < 0.05$). Video-Mac VL dramatically shortened the time necessary for effective endotracheal tube installation compared to DL. The GlideScope and Video Mac needed fewer intubation attempts ($P < .05$). In their study, Shalaka R Sonavane, Sunil K Gvalanil, and Pratika Bhokare [10] divided 200 patients into two groups: I and II. Group I consisted of patients receiving general anesthesia with endotracheal intubation using a conventional Macintosh blade, while group II consisted of patients using King Vision (KV) VL. The hemodynamic response to laryngoscopy and intubation was greatly reduced by KV VL. Also, KV VL had greater glottic visibility and required less maneuvering during laryngoscopy. Based on their comparison of Macintosh and KV VL, they determined that KV VL was more successful in regulating hemodynamic response to intubation and required fewer external procedures.

Kurt Reutzler and team [11] performed a randomized controlled experiment on 130 obese surgery patients, employing both a McGrath video laryngoscope and a direct laryngoscope during intubation. The McGrath video laryngoscope demonstrated much superior glottis visibility than the Macintosh direct laryngoscope for intubation in morbidly obese individuals. Bjoern Hossfeld and team [12] conducted an observational comparative research of C-Mac PM VL vs Direct laryngoscope on 228 out-of-hospital emergency patients requiring endotracheal intubation. The study removed five individuals because they utilized indirect laryngoscope blades. Out of 223 patients, 120 had a glottic view with a Cormack and Lehane grade of II to IV obtained using direct laryngoscopy. The C-MAC PM video laryngoscope considerably enhanced glottis visibility for these patients ($P < 0.001$). In 56 individuals, there was a substantial improvement in glottic vision ($P < 0.001$).

Andre van Zundert and team [13] studied 450 patients having elective surgery intubation and compared three video laryngoscopes (VLs): the GlideScope Ranger, the V-MAC Storz, and the McGrath. All three VLs provided a superior glottic vision than the standard laryngoscope. The average intubation time was 34 +/- 20 seconds for the GlideScope, 18 +/- 12 seconds for the V-MAC Storz, and 38 +/- 23 seconds for the McGrath VLs. The Storz VLs allowed for substantially quicker intubation than the other two VLs. A stylet was required in 7% of Storz patients, compared to around 50% of the other two VLS groups. The study revealed that, while VLs provide additional benefits, such as improved glottic visibility and intubation circumstances, a good laryngeal view does not ensure straightforward tracheal tube

insertion and necessitates the use of a stylet. Shahnaz Shayeghi and team [14] studied 64 newborns scheduled for elective surgery needing general anesthesia and compared their hemodynamic stress responses to VL and DL. There were no significant differences seen between the two groups. Ali Reza Pournajafian and team [15] conducted a comprehensive randomized experiment to compare the hemodynamic stress responses to laryngoscopy and tracheal intubation in Glidescope and Macintosh laryngoscope patients undergoing general anesthesia for elective procedures. The hemodynamic responses of the two groups did not differ significantly at any time point. Yokose et al. found that McGRATH MAC video laryngoscopy might lower the incidence of hypertension following tracheal intubation when compared to Macintosh laryngoscopy. Liu ZJ et al. discovered that McGRATH MAC video laryngoscopy caused a lower rise in systolic blood pressure following intubation [16]. Although video laryngoscopy gives a clearer view of the upper airways, making endotracheal intubation easier, its hemodynamic implications are yet unclear. Despite having few restrictions, video laryngoscopes have become the primary backup equipment in situations of unsuccessful intubation efforts or expected difficult intubation.

Conclusion

It is concluded that videolaryngoscope substantially reduces the time required for intubation and improves the visualization of the glottis in patients who require general anesthesia for surgery when compared to the direct laryngoscope for endotracheal intubation.

References

1. Sinha R, Sharma A, Ray BR, Kumar Pandey R, Darlong V, Punj J, et al. Comparison of the Success of Two Techniques for the Endotracheal Intubation with C-MAC Video Laryngoscope Miller Blade in Children: A Prospective Randomized Study. *Anesthesiol Res Pract*. 2016; 2016:4196813
2. Myatra SN, Patwa A, Divatia JV. Videolaryngoscopy for all intubations: Is direct laryngoscopy obsolete? *Indian J Anaesth*. 2022; 66(3):169–73.
3. Rabiner JE, Auerbach M, Avner JR, Daswani D, Khine H. Comparison of GlideScope Videolaryngoscopy to Direct Laryngoscopy for Intubation of a Pediatric Simulator by Novice Physicians. *Emerg Med Int*. 2013; 2013:407547.
4. Bhalla A. *AIIMS-MAMC-PGI's Comprehensive Textbook of Diagnostic Radiology (3 Volumes)*. Jp Medical Ltd; 2017. p. 2036

5. Kaplan MB, Ward DS, Berci G. A new video laryngoscope-an aid to intubation and teaching. *J Clin Anesth.* 2002; 14(8):620–6.
6. Zhou M, Xi X, Li M, Wang S, Liu Z, Liu JQ. Video Laryngoscopy Improves the Success of Neonatal Tracheal Intubation for Novices but Not for Experienced Medical Staff. *Front Pediatr.* 2020; 8:445
7. Koorosh Ahmadi, Mohsen Ebrahimi, Amir Masoud Hashemian, Saeed Sarshar, Vafa Rahimi-Movaghar. GlideScope Video Laryngoscope for Difficult Intubation in Emergency Patients: a Quasi-Randomized Controlled Trial ; December 2015 53(12):738-742
8. Maria Michailidou, Terence O'Keeffe, Jarrod M Mosier, Randall S Friese, Bellal Joseph, Peter Rhee, John C Sakles; A comparison of video laryngoscopy to direct laryngoscopy for the emergency intubation of trauma patients. *World J Surg;* 2015 Mar; 39(3):782-8.
9. Roya Yumul, Ofelia L.Elvir-Lazo, Paul F. White, Alejandro Sloninsky, Marshal Kaplan, Robert Kariger, Robert Naruse, Nathaniel Parker, Christine Pham, Xiao Zhang; Comparison of three video laryngoscopy devices to direct laryngoscopy for intubating obese patients: a randomized controlled trial ; *J Clin Anesth;* 2016 Jun;31:71-7
10. Shalaka R sonavane, Sunil K Gvalanil and Pratika bhokare; Comparison between Conventional Macintosh Laryngoscope and King Vision Video Laryngoscope in Endotracheal Intubation for Elective Surgeries: A Prospective Randomized Study.
11. Kurt Ruetzler, Eva Rivas, Barak Cohen, Lauretta Mosteller, Adriana Martin, Allen Keebler, Kamal Maheshwari, Karen Steckner, Mi Wang, Chahar Praveen, Sandeep Khanna, Natallya Makarova, Daniel I. Sessier and Alparslan Turan; McGrath Video Laryngoscope Versus Macintosh Direct Laryngoscopy for Intubation of Morbidly Obese Patients: A Randomized Trial; *Anesth Analg;* 2020 Aug;131(2):586-593.
12. Bjoern Hossfeld, Kristina Frey, Volker Doriges, Lorenz Lampl and Matthias Helm; Improvement in glottic visualisation by using the C-MAC PM video laryngoscope as a first-line device for out-of-hospital emergency tracheal intubation: An observational study; *Eur J Anaesthesiol.* 2015 Jun; 32(6):425-31.
13. André van Zundert , Ralph Maassen, Ruben Lee, Remi Willems, Michel Timmerman, Marc Siemonsma, Marc Buise, Marco Wiepking ; A Macintosh laryngoscope blade for videolaryngoscopy reduces stylet use in patients with normal airways. *Anesth Analg.* 2009 Sep; 109(3):825-31.
14. Shahnaz Shayeghi, Afsaneh Sadeghi, Sayed Sajjad Razavi, Mehdi Ghasemi. Hemodynamic responses to orotracheal intubation with a video laryngoscope in infants: A comparison study. *J Res Med Sci.* September 2007; 12(5): 251-256.
15. Ali Reza Pournajafian, Mohammad Reza Ghodraty, Seyed Hamid Reza Faiz, Hamidreza Goodarzynejad and Enseyeh Dogmehchi; Comparing GlideScope Video, Laryngoscope and Macintosh Laryngoscope regarding Hemodynamic Responses during Orotracheal Intubation: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Iranian Red Crescent; Med J.* 2014 April; 16(4): e12334.
16. Stephen R Collins. Direct and Indirect Laryngoscopy: Equipment and Techniques.rc.rc journal.com/content/resp/59/6/850